

Radio Gd-Distance Number of Some Basic Graph

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published online: 26 July 2023</p> <p>Corresponding Name K. John Bosco</p>	<p>A Radio Gd-distance labeling of a connected graph G is an injective map f from the vertex set $V(G)$ to \mathbb{N} such that for two distinct vertices u and v of G, $d^{Gd}(u,v) + f(u) - f(v) \geq 1 + diam^{Gd}(G)$, where $d^{Gd}(u,v)$ denotes the Gd-distance between u and v and $diam^{Gd}(G)$ denotes the Gd-diameter of G. The Radio Gd-distance number of f, (f) is the maximum label assigned to any vertex of G. The Radio Gd-distance number of G, $rn(G)$ is the minimum value f of G. In this paper we find the radio Gd-distance number of some basic graph.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: Gd-distance, Radio Gd-distance, Radio Gd-distance number.</p>	

I. INTRODUCTION

By a graph $G = (V(G), E(G))$ we mean a finite undirected graph without loops or multiple edges. Let $V(G)$ and $E(G)$ denotes the vertex set and edge set of G . The order and size of G are denoted by p and q respectively.

The Gd-distance was introduced by V. Maheswari and M. Joice Mabel. If u and v are vertices of a connected graph G , Gd-length of a u - v path is defined as $d^{Gd}(u, v) = d(u, v) + \deg(u) + \deg(v)$. The Gd-radius, denoted by $r^{Gd}(G) = \min\{e^{Gd}(v) : v \in V(G)\}$. Similarly the Gd-diameter $d^{Gd}(G) = \max\{e^{Gd}(v) : v \in V(G)\}$. We observe that for any two vertices u and v of G we have $d(u,v) \leq d^{Gd}(u, v)$. The equality holds if and only if u, v are identical. If G is any connected graph, then the d^{Gd} distance is a metric on the set of vertices of G . We can check easily that for any non-trivial connected graph, $r^{Gd}(G) \leq d^{Gd}(G) \leq 2r^{Gd}(G)$. The lower bound is clear From the definition and the upper bound follows from the triangular inequality.

In this paper, we introduced the concept of radio Gd-distance labeling of a graph G . Radio Gd-distance labeling is a function f from $V(G)$ to \mathbb{N} satisfying the condition $d^{Gd}(u, v) + |f(u) - f(v)| \geq 1 + diam^{Gd}(G)$, where $diam^{Gd}(G)$ is the Gd-distance diameter of G . A Gd-distance radio labeling number of G is the maximum label assigned to any vertex of G . It is denoted by $rn^{Gd}(G)$

Radio labeling can be regarded as an extension of distance-two labeling which is motivated by the channel assignment problem introduced by W. K. Hale [6]. G. Chartrand et al.[2] introduced the concept of radio labeling of graph. Also G. Chartrand et al.[3] gave the upper bound for the radio number of path. The exact value for the radio number of path and cycle was given by Liu and Zhu [10]. However G. Chartrand et al.[2] obtained different values for them. They found the lower and upper bound for the radio number of cycle. Liu [9] gave the lower bound for the radio number of Tree. The exact value for the radio number of Hypercube was given by R. Khennoufa and O. Togni [8]. In [4] C. Fernandez et al. found the radio number for complete graph, Star graph, Complete Bipartite graph, Wheel graph and Gear graph. In this paper, we find the radio Gd-distance labeling of some basic graphs.

II. MAIN RESULTS

Theorem 2.1

The radio Gd-distance number of the complete graph, $rn^{Gd}(K_n) = n \forall n$

Proof.

Let, $V(K_n) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ be the vertex set

Then, $d^{Gd}(v_i, v_j) = 2n - 1$ for $1 \leq i, j \leq n$

It is obvious that the $diam^{Gd}(K_n) = 2n - 1$.

The radio Gd-distance condition is $d^{Gd}(u, v) + |f(u) - f(v)| \geq 1 + diam^{Gd}(G) = 2n$

Now, fix $f(v_1) = 1$

$$d^{Gd}(v_1, v_2) + |f(v_1) - f(v_2)| \geq 2n - 1 + |1 - f(v_2)| \geq 2n$$

$|1 - f(v_2)| \geq 1$, which implies $f(v_2) = 2$

$\therefore f(v_i) = i, 1 \leq i \leq n$

Hence, $rn^{Gd}(K_n) = n, \forall n$

Theorem 2.2

The radio Gd-distance number of a star graph, $rn^{Gd}(K_{1,n}) = n^2 - 2n + 2, n \geq 3$

Proof.

Let $V(K_{1,n}) = \{v_0, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ be the vertex set, where v_0 be the central vertex and

$E(K_{1,n}) = \{v_0 v_i; 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ be the edge set

Then, $d^{Gd}(v_0, v_i) = n + 2; 1 \leq i \leq n, d^{Gd}(v_i, v_j) = 4; 1 \leq i, j \leq n; i \neq j$

So, $diam^{Gd}(K_{1,n}) = n + 2$

Without loss of generality,

$$f(v_1) < f(v_0) < f(v_2) < \dots < f(v_n)$$

We shall check the radio Gd-distance condition

$$d^{Gd}(u, v) + |f(u) - f(v)| \geq 1 + diam^{Gd}(G) = n + 3$$

Fix $f(v_1) = 1$, for (v_1, v_0)

$$d^{Gd}(v_1, v_0) + |f(v_1) - f(v_0)| \geq n + 2 + |1 - f(v_0)| \geq n + 3$$

$|1 - f(v_0)| \geq 1$, which implies $f(v_0) = 2$

For (v_1, v_2)

$$d^{Gd}(v_1, v_2) + |f(v_1) - f(v_2)| \geq 4 + |1 - f(v_2)| \geq n + 3$$

$|1 - f(v_2)| \geq n - 1$, which implies $f(v_2) = n$

For (v_2, v_3)

$$d^{Gd}(v_2, v_3) + |f(v_2) - f(v_3)| \geq 4 + |n - f(v_3)| \geq n + 3$$

$|n - f(v_3)| \geq n - 1$, which implies $f(v_3) = 2n - 1$

$\therefore f(v_i) = n(i - 1) - i + 2, 1 \leq i \leq n$

Hence, $rn^{Gd}(K_{1,n}) = n^2 - 2n + 2, n \geq 3$

Theorem 2.3

The radio Gd-distance number of a path $rn^{Gd}(P_n) \leq n^2 - 5n + 8, n \geq 4$

Proof.

Let $V(P_n) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ be the vertex set and $E(P_n) = \{v_i v_{i+1}; 1 \leq i \leq n - 1\}$ be the edge set

Then, $d^{Gd}(v_1, v_n) = d^{Gd}(v_2, v_n) = n + 1$,

$$d^{Gd}(v_1, v_2) = d^{Gd}(v_{n-1}, v_n) = 4,$$

$$d^{Gd}(v_i, v_{i+1}) = 5; 2 \leq i \leq n - 2$$

It is clear that $diam^{Gd}(P_n) = n + 1$

Without loss of generality

$$f(v_1) < f(v_n) < f(v_2) < \dots < f(v_{n-1})$$

We shall check the radio Gd-distane condition

$$d^{Gd}(u, v) + |f(u) - f(v)| \geq 1 + diam^{Gd}(G) = n + 2$$

Fix $f(v_1) = 1$ for (v_1, v_n)

$$d^{Gd}(v_1, v_n) + |f(v_1) - f(v_n)| \geq n + 1 + |1 - f(v_n)| \geq n + 2$$

$|1 - f(v_n)| \geq 1$, which implies $f(v_n) = 2$

For (v_1, v_2)

$$d^{Gd}(v_1, v_2) + |f(v_1) - f(v_2)| \geq 4 + |1 - f(v_2)| \geq n + 2$$

$|1 - f(v_2)| \geq n - 2$, which implies $f(v_2) = n - 1$

For (v_2, v_3)

$$d^{Gd}(v_2, v_3) + |f(v_2) - f(v_3)| \geq 5 + |n - 1 - f(v_3)| \geq n + 2$$

$|n - 1 - f(v_3)| \geq n - 3$, which implies $f(v_3) = 2n - 4$

$\therefore f(v_i) = n(i - 1) - 3i + 5, 2 \leq i \leq n - 1$

Hence, $rn^{Gd}(P_n) \leq n^2 - 5n + 8, n \geq 4$

Note. $rn^{Gd}(P_n) = 3$ if $n=3$

Theorem 4

The radio Gd-distance number of a subdivision of a star, $rn^{Gd}S(K_{1,n}) = 2n^2 - 5n + 3, n \geq 3$

Proof

Let $V(S(K_{1,n})) = \{v_0, v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n, u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n\}$ be the vertex set, where v_0 is the central vertex and $E(S(K_{1,n})) = \{v_0 u_i, v_i u_i; 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ be the edge set

Then, $d^{Gd}(v_0, v_i) = d^{Gd}(v_0, u_i) = n + 3; 1 \leq i \leq n, d^{Gd}(v_i, v_{i+1}) = d^{Gd}(u_i, u_{i+1}) = 6; 1 \leq i \leq n$

$$d^{Gd}(v_i, u_i) = 4; 1 \leq i \leq n$$

It is clear that $diam^{Gd}(S(K_{1,n})) = n + 3$

Without loss of generality $f(u_1) < f(v_0) < f(u_2) < \dots < f(u_n) < f(v_1) < \dots < f(v_n)$

We shall check the radio Gd-distance condition

$$d^{Gd}(u, v) + |f(u) - f(v)| \geq 1 + diam^{Gd}(G) = n + 4$$

Fix $f(u_1) = 1$, for $(u_1, v_0) 1 \leq i \leq n$

$$d^{Gd}(u_1, v_0) + |f(u_1) - f(v_0)| \geq n + 3 + |1 - f(v_0)| \geq n + 4$$

$|1 - f(v_0)| \geq 1$ which implies $f(v_0) = 2$

For (u_1, u_2)

$$d^{Gd}(u_1, u_2) + |f(u_1) - f(u_2)| \geq 6 + |1 - f(u_2)| \geq n + 4$$

$|2 - f(u_2)| \geq n - 2$, which implies $f(u_2) = n - 1$

For (u_2, u_3)

$$d^{Gd}(u_2, u_3) + |f(u_2) - f(u_3)| \geq 6 + |n - 1 - f(u_3)| \geq n + 4$$

$|n - 1 - f(u_3)| \geq n - 2$, which implies $f(u_3) = 2n - 3$

$$\therefore f(u_i) = n(i - 1) - 2i + 3, 1 \leq i \leq n$$

Therefore, $f(u_n) = n^2 - 3n + 3$

For $(u_n, v_i), 1 \leq i \leq n$

$$d^{Gd}(u_n, v_1) + |f(u_n) - f(v_1)| \geq 6 + |n^2 - 3n + 3 - f(v_1)| \geq n + 4$$

$$|n^2 - 3n + 3 - f(v_1)| \geq n - 2 \text{ which implies } f(v_1) = n^2 - 2n + 1$$

For (v_1, v_2)

$$d^{Gd}(v_1, v_2) + |f(v_1) - f(v_2)| \geq 6 + |n^2 - 2n + 1 - f(v_2)| \geq n + 4$$

$$|n^2 - 2n + 1 - f(v_2)| \geq n - 2, \text{ which implies } f(v_2) = n^2 - n - 1$$

$$\therefore f(v_i) = n^2 + n(i - 3) - 2i + 3, 1 \leq i \leq n$$

Hence, $rn^{Gd}S(K_{1,n}) = 2n^2 - 5n + 3, n \geq 4$

Note. $rn^{Gd}S(K_{1,n}) = 2n + 1$ if $n = 2, 3$

Theorem 5

The radio Gd-distance number of bistar graph, $rn^{Gd}(B_{n,n}) = 4n^2 - 3n + 4, n \geq 2$

Proof.

Let, $V(B_{n,n}) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n, x_1, x_2, u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n\}$ be the vertex set

and $E(B_{n,n}) = \{x_1u_i, x_2v_i, x_1x_2; 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ be the edge set

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Then, } d^{Gd}(x_1, u_i) &= d^{Gd}(x_2, v_i) = n + 3; 1 \leq i \leq n, \\ d^{Gd}(x_1, x_2) &= 2n + 3, d^{Gd}(u_i, v_j) = 5; 1 \leq i, j \leq n, \\ i \neq j, d^{Gd}(u_i, u_j) &= d^{Gd}(v_i, v_j) = 4; 1 \leq i, j \leq n, \\ i \neq j, d^{Gd}(x_1, v_i) &= d^{Gd}(x_2, u_i) = n + 4; 1 \leq i \leq n \end{aligned}$$

It is clear that $diam^{Gd}(B_{n,n}) = 2n + 3$

Without loss of generality $f(v_1) < f(u_1) < f(v_2) < f(u_2) < \dots < f(v_n) < f(u_n) < f(x_2) < f(x_1)$

We shall check the radio Gd-distance condition

$$d^{Gd}(u, v) + |f(u) - f(v)| \geq 1 + diam^{Gd}(G) = 2n + 4$$

Fix, $f(v_1) = 1$, For $(v_i, u_i), 1 \leq i \leq n$

$$d^{Gd}(v_1, u_1) + |f(v_1) - f(u_1)| \geq 5 + |1 - f(u_1)| \geq 2n + 4$$

$|1 - f(u_1)| \geq 2n - 1$, which implies $f(u_1) = 2n$

For $(u_i, v_{i+1}), 1 \leq i \leq n - 1$

$$d^{Gd}(u_1, v_2) + |f(u_1) - f(v_2)| \geq 5 + |2n - f(v_2)| \geq 2n + 4$$

$|2n - f(v_2)| \geq 2n - 1$ which implies $f(v_2) = 4n - 1$

For (v_2, u_2)

$$d^{Gd}(v_2, u_2) + |f(v_2) - f(u_2)| \geq 5 + |4n - 1 - f(u_2)| \geq 2n + 4$$

$|4n - 1 - f(u_2)| \geq 2n - 1$, which implies $f(u_2) = 6n - 2$

$$\therefore f(u_i) = n(4i - 2) - 2i + 2, 1 \leq i \leq n$$

$$f(v_i) = n(4i - 4) - 2i + 3, 1 \leq i \leq n$$

Therefore, $f(u_n) = 4n^2 - 4n + 2$

For (u_n, x_2)

$$d^{Gd}(u_n, x_2) + |f(u_n) - f(x_2)| \geq n + 3 + |4n^2 - 4n + 2 - f(x_2)| \geq 2n + 4$$

$|4n^2 - 4n + 2 - f(x_2)| \geq n + 1$, which implies $f(x_2) = 4n^2 - 3n + 3$

For (x_2, x_1)

$$d^{Gd}(x_2, x_1) + |f(x_2) - f(x_1)| \geq 2n + 3 + |4n^2 - 3n + 3 - f(x_1)| \geq 2n + 4$$

$|4n^2 - 3n + 3 - f(x_1)| \geq 2n$, which implies $f(x_1) = 4n^2 - 3n + 4$

Hence, $rn^{Gd}(B_{n,n}) = 4n^2 - 3n + 4, n \geq 2$

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